

MECHANISM FOR IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SPECIALIST AGRONOMISTS

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Abstract. *This article describes the basis of the understanding and acceptance of individuality, its formation and active approach to improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists.*

Keywords: *person-oriented, professional competence, active approach, methodology, professional competence, integrative approach.*

Professional training of future specialists, i.e. their professionalism and competence, is specially recognized in the coordination and improvement of higher education processes with modern developments. Because modern requirements in the direction of ensuring the effectiveness of the processes of training qualified personnel provide for the effective organization of innovative and integrated educational processes that serve to form and develop the professional competence of future specialists.

The use of person-oriented, professional-active, personal-active approaches in improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists was carried out in acoci.

In the process of improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists, international educational standards, the labor market and the requirements of the state customer, i.e. the level of professional training of students, are taken into account.

In the process of improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists, the principles related to professional activity are formed in acocida munocabat: active approach, innovation, information, development of thinking, creativity, democratization of education, the principle of individual orientation, the principle of cooperation, the principle of equality, the principle of constructivity, universal values in acocida munocabat, communication is installed.

It is necessary to educate the professional competence of future specialist agronomists in the spirit of national values, traditions, and national attitudes. Improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists is defined as the task of determining the professional-pedagogical requirements, the level of competence, defining the mechanisms, developing an integrated structure of improvement, and determining the components of improving their readiness for the job according to the level of professional training.

Improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists is primarily related to the formation of personality. In this case, the system-forming factor of professional training becomes a motivational and valuable factor, it determines the social and professional status of the specialist, and creates an opportunity to implement the anthropocentric principle in his work. Predominance of broad social and entrepreneurial motives in students allows to support and develop the individuality of the student, to know personal interests and possibilities.

Factors that develop creativity skills in improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists: development of creative thinking skills, formation of creative activity, traceability of the educational process and strengthening of problematic research directions;

organization of situations for creative problem solving and development of creative activities of students; to achieve students' approach to the experience of creative activity as a practical necessity and a structural element of the content of creative activity in the future; directing the development of students' professional skills and abilities to the development of interactive methods and technologies, independent creative activities, independent knowledge acquisition, self-education, self-knowledge, self-possession, activation of students' independent work abilities, in this process achieve their creative thinking; it was found that it consists of creating a favorable creative cooperation environment for students to show their creative abilities.

Improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists is related to the understanding and acceptance of individual uniqueness, and in order to form it, it is necessary to develop professional training.

In this case, a person-oriented and active approach, the system of activities developed in ACOC is described with a practical orientation and allows students to be involved in real interaction. It helps to improve the motivational-value character in practical skills and competencies, personal qualities and attitudes.

An active approach to improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists will help to separate the learning and practical activities necessary for the future agronomist to solve real tasks in professional activity. The professional-activity approach allows to model and design the activities of the future specialist.

The personality-activist approach relies on the psychological theory of personality. The use of this approach stimulates students' professional education and self-development, their independent work on mastering pedagogical skills, and its professional qualities are supported.

Modeling, business and role-playing games, creative and practical assignments, trainings can be used in the set of vocitas that improve the professional competence of future specialist agronomists.

Improvement of the communicative-technological component in improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists is of great importance for the formation of the overall composition of professional training.

In improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists, emotional experiences in the structure of the student's professional self-awareness control his behavior and activities. In this way, the motivations for mutual respect arise in the context of social interaction and social creativity. The intellectual-cognitive component in improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists is related to the improvement of intellectual-heuristic and intellectual-logical skills, and the set of skills ensures the implementation of research activities, professional training in improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists.

During the internship, which ensures interaction with the practical activities of the future specialist agronomists, the student of higher education was directed to the systematic implementation of the process of managing the student according to the goal during the internship.

In improving the professional competence of future specialist agronomists, in preparation for professional activity, the practical exchange of individual experience, the establishment of a form of professional practice, and the establishment of professional development in cooperation will develop their skills and competence.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". September 23, 2020: <https://lex.uz/docs/5013007>
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022 "On the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" PF-60-con
3. Decree PF-4947-con of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On Strategic Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T., 2017. - 6th con. - Article 70.
4. Decision PQ-2909-con of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the higher education system". 20 of 2017 appeal.
5. Akramova F.A., Lutfullaeva N.Kh, Khaidarova Kh.P. "Pedagogical psychology" science (text of lectures). - T.: TDIU, 2005 - 201 pages.
6. Андреева Г.М. Социальная психология.- М., 1996. - 376 с.
7. Асқарова М, Matchonov С. and others. Turn off the speech of young children. Т. : "Uzbekiston"-2001. -160 p.
8. Ahmedova N. M. Improving professional training of future teachers in the interactive approach // Ped. science. doc (PhD). dicc. abstract-T. 2021. -16 p.
9. Байкова Л.А.,Гребенкина Л.К. Педагогическое мастерство и педагогические технологии. -М. , 2001. -256 с.
10. Baybekova G. D. The educational and moral views of the enlighteners of the Middle Ages at the beginning of the 19th century: Ped. Doctor of Sciences. dicc. -Tashkent, 2002. -236b.